

Advantages of chooser intelligence in sexual selection

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Abstract

Mate choice is hinged on the fundamental question: which traits to choose and why? This question is key to understanding how genetic variation is maintained in populations subjected to sexual selection, and resolving the so-called lek paradox. Recent work has demonstrated that using correlated strategies, that is, choice mediated by a randomly changing environmental variable is hugely advantageous; it also conjectures that predicting this variable may be advantageous as well, giving rise to chooser intelligence. Here we confirm this hypothesis using individual-based simulation. Several strategies are pitted against each other: choosing based on an external variable that itself changes every few generations; or choosing based on its value the next generations, or, more generally, k generations ahead; as well as random choice. All the strategies except the random choice are costly. Larger values of k consistently win. This shows that if the choice is based on a predictable environmental variable, then it is advantageous to develop the ability to predict it and to base the choice on this variable. Thus, an evolutionary path to chooser intelligence is demonstrated.

1 Introduction

Exuberance of sexually selected traits has attracted the interest of researchers since the times of Darwin (1871). Fisher's runaway (or sexy sons) hypothesis (Fisher, 1915) provides an explanation: choosing a trait provides an advantage for the son that is going to be chosen, making the choice advantageous itself. However, it only works if not everyone chooses the same: if the choice

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is uniform, as would happen if the chosen trait spreads over the population, the advantage collapses (the so-called lek paradox (?)). Mate choice is thus a curious game: one should choose what others choose, yet not what everyone chooses. Moreover, the game is predictive as it is played over what will happen over next generations: the advantages of the choice at the current generation are only conferred to the children. Therefore, to understand the evolution of mate choice it is necessary to figure out the dynamics of what traits are picked to be chosen and why.

Correlated strategies, proposed in (Ryabko et al., 2023), offer a solution. Mate choice is based on an external variable that can be observed by all members of the population, such as an environmental cue, which is called the beacon. If this beacon changes every few generations, then the resulting variability is sufficient to make the choice based on it advantageous, even in the presence of very high (artificially inflated in the model) cost of choice. In the model of (Ryabko et al., 2023), the beacon takes the form of the male ornament, and the females that use this observation compare the males that they can choose from to this ideal (beacon) mate.

Note that the external observable variable crystallizes the predictive aspect of choice: if some of the choosers manage to predict it then they should choose based on the prediction rather than on the current observation. Thus, it is conjectured by Ryabko et al. (2023) that mate choice is a path to chooser intelligence: it is advantageous to develop sufficient intelligence to predict the beacon.

Here we confirm this hypothesis using an individual-based simulation model. Rather than modeling intelligence, we implement directly strategies that have an access to the next state of the beacon, and choose based on this next state. Several concurrent strategies are considered: the random choice, which is costless; the beacon strategy, that chooses according to the current value of the observable beacon; and predictive strategies, that, for each value of k , choose based on the value of the beacon k steps ahead. The beacon itself is a simple counter that increments every l generations, for some fixed parameter l until reaching a maximum value where it resets to 0. In the simplest case, the beacon is 000111000... (here $l = 3$).

2 The model

An individual-based simulation model is employed to study the viability of the predictive strategies, mostly following Ryabko et al. (2023) with some differences.

The model is based on a constant-size population and discrete generations. The population consists of S individuals, each characterized by their alleles at the following haploid loci. The ornament locus, which is only expressed in the male, has alleles ranging from 0 to V . The strategy locus,

which is only expressed in the female, also has various alleles, ranging from 0 to K , with 0 being random choice and the other alleles representing the predictive strategies.

On each generation, reproduction, mutation and decimation take place.

The *reproduction* is performed by selecting randomly a female among those currently alive, who then breeds and produces two offspring, one male and one female; the next female is selected and the process is repeated until S offspring are produced (i.e., the next generation is filled). The *breeding* follows the so-called (Janetos, 1980) *best-of- N* model, that is, each female is presented with a pool of N randomly selected males to make a choice from. The female chooses according to her strategy (the allele at the corresponding locus), as described below. Each offspring inherits the strategy from one of the parents with equal probability. The same goes for the the ornament.

Mutation in the offspring is performed independently on each locus, with probabilities m for the ornament and m_s for the strategy. The *decimation* takes place both on females and males: each female is taken out of the reproductive pool (killed) with a certain probability c which is the *cost of her strategy*. The cost of the random strategy is always set to 0, while the cost of the predictive strategy is some value $c \in (0, 1)$. For the sake of compatibility with previous models in the literature, there is a small decimation on the males, with the probability c_m of being killed proportional to the number of 1s in the ornament (thus slightly pushing towards the all-zeros ornament).

2.1 Predictive strategies

The female strategies are: the random strategy, which is simply selecting a random male from the batch given, and the *predictive beacon* strategies. These are correlated strategies based on a single external variable called *the beacon*. This variable starts at 0 at generation 0 and increments every l generations, where l is a parameter we call *the lag*, until it reaches the maximal value V (the maximal ornament value), after which it resets. In the simplest case $V = 1$ and so the beacon is 0 for l generations, followed by 1 for l generations and so on. Thus, the beacon value b_G at generation G is defined by the following formula:

$$b_G = \lfloor G/l \rfloor \pmod V,$$

where G is the current generation number. This means that the beacon is highly predictable, rather than being random as in Ryabko et al. (2023).

For example, with $l = 4$ and $V = 3$ the sequence of the beacon values looks like this:

$$00001111222200001111\dots \tag{1}$$

The predictive beacon strategies use this in a straightforward manner. The strategy 1 favors the males whose ornament is closest to the current beacon

b_G . Each next strategy, instead of the beacon, uses the value of the beacon at the next generation; thus, strategy s chooses the males whose ornament is closest to the b_{G+s-1} . To continue the example above, the sequence of male ornament alleles (values) favored by the strategies 2 and 3 at successive generations would be

$$00011112222000011110... \quad (2)$$

and

$$00111122220000111100... \quad (3)$$

respectively.

To recoup, (1) represents the sequence of the environmental observations on successive generations; each of this is used, on the corresponding generations, by females with strategy 1 to base their choice of the male ornament. Similarly, (2) and (3) represent the *predictions* of the sequence (1) made by females with strategies 2 and 3 (respectively) on successive generations, 1 and 2 generations ahead. The females with these strategies base their choice of the male ornament on these predictions. Thus, in this example, on generation 3, females with strategies 1 and 2 choose males with ornament 0, and females with strategy 2 choose males with ornament 1. On generation 4, females with strategies 1 choose males with ornament 0, and females with strategy 1 and 2 choose males with ornament 1. On generation 5, females with strategy 1, 2 and 3 choose males with ornament 1.

Note that we do not attempt to model the evolution of intelligence *per se*. Instead, the predictive strategies are assumed to have evolved and their performance is measured.

2.2 Estimating viability

The viability of the predictive strategies is evaluated by running them against each other as well as against the random-choice strategy. In the experiments, the random-choice strategy always has the cost of 0, while the predictive strategies have a constant non-zero cost (the same for all strategies). A different number of strategies is run in different experiments.

The initial population is set up in a uniformly random fashion: both the strategies and the ornaments are filled uniformly at random. Different initializations (as in Ryabko et al. (2023)) are possible, but these were not found to be important for these experiments.

Table 1 summarizes the parameters of the model. Some parameters are fixed throughout the experiments: the population size, the sex ratio, the batch size used for male selection. Other parameters are varied, including the beacon parameter l (the lag) and the number of alleles V in the ornament.

Table 1: Parameters of the model

Notation	Parameter	Value(s) used in the experiments; bold for the main one
S	Population size	2000, constant 1:1 sex ratio
V	Number of different alleles in the ornament	2, 5
c	Cost (mortality rate) of the choosy strategy	0.05 0.1
c_m	Cost (mortality rate) of males	$0.01 \times$ average ornament attribute
N	Batch size: number of males a female can choose from	20
m	Attribute mutation rate, ornament and beacon ornament	0.01
m_s	Strategy mutation rate	0.01
T	Total number of generations	5000

Parameters of the beacon

l	The lag: how many generations the beacon does not change	5
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3 Results

The experiments show that the strategy that predicts the farthest is the most advantageous. This advantage collapses when the first strategy starts to be a reasonable predictor for the last. This is because the beacon forms a complete cycle over $l * V$ generations (the lag of the beacon times the number of values it takes, which is the same as the number of alleles in the ornament). Interestingly, when only one beacon strategy is present, it fares slightly worse than the last predictive strategy when more than one (but not many enough to close the cycle) are present.

The charts below summarize these findings.

Figure 1: The ratio of each strategy after 5000 generations, averaged over 30 runs. The first strategy is always the random strategy. The first non-random strategy follows the beacon at the current generation; each next strategy predicts by one more generation. The ornament is binary ($V = 2$). The beacon lag $l=5$ (beacon changes every 5 generations). This gives the beacon cycle (period) of 10. Different plots correspond to different number of strategies pitted against each other. The cost of choosy strategies is $c = 0.05$.

Figure 2: Same as in the previous figure, but there are 5 alleles in the ornament ($V = 5$) and the beacon lag $l = 3$. This gives the beacon cycle (period) of 15. The cost of choosy strategies is $c = 0.1$.

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